

Annual report CAA Netherlands-Flanders chapter (CAA-NL-FL) 2020

Board:

Chair: Ronald Visser

Secretary: Jitte Waagen

Treasurer: Devi Taelman

Communications officer: Alex Brandsen

The year in which the world changed... While many members of CAA_NL-FL prepared sessions or presentations for the annual CAA meeting in Oxford, the Covid-19 situation made this impossible.

The active role of our members in the international CAA is often clearly visible during the conference. Many of the contributions by our members were often in collaboration with people from all over the globe, showing that our chapter plays an active role in the international community

We planned to organize a day of workshops in cooperation with the Digital Archaeology Group from Leiden University and Groningen University in Groningen in April 2019, but this failed due to Covid-19.

We have updated our statutes to comply with the latest developments on privacy and ethics, as well as created the possibility for holding a virtual GM, as to be able to function without a physical meeting, and to be able to add a fourth board member. (<https://www.caanfl.nl/?q=node/77>)

Alex Brandsen from UL (<https://www.universiteitleiden.nl/en/staffmembers/alex-brandsen#tab-1>) has been added to the CAA-NL-FL board and to help with organising new events and updating our communication channels. Formally, a new member is voted on during the GM at the CAA-NL-FL event, but this has taken place online and he was unanimously voted in as our new board member.

On the 3rd and 4th of December, we managed to have our biannual Joint Chapter Meeting at Saxion University of Applied Sciences in Deventer. The aim was an in-person meeting, but the result was a successful online event with 187 registrations from all over the world. The contributions were not only from members of CAA-DE or CAA-NL-FL, but also from America, Australia, and other countries.

Topics for the sessions were:

- Machine learning, AI;
- Remote sensing and geophysics;
- Gaming, AR and VR;
- Tools, statistics, and little Minions.

The effect of an online meeting was that we had more visitors that would normally not visit a CAA conference and this resulted in many new members for both our chapters. The participants came from various parts of the work field. There were not only academics and students, but also people working for the local government, commercial companies, and self-employed archaeologists.

Finally, CAA-NL-FL together with Philip Verhagen put together a bid for the organisation of the 50-year anniversary edition of CAA in Amsterdam, hosted by the University of Amsterdam in 2023. The conference will represent the whole of Dutch and Flemish digital archaeology through CAA-NL-FL, and involve the participation of Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, the universities of Leiden, Groningen, and Saxion University of Applied Sciences in the Netherlands, and the universities of Ghent, Antwerp, Leuven and Vrije Universiteit Brussel in Belgium. The bid was accepted at the Virtual AGM 26-9-2020.